

Top Level Taxonomy of Bias: Systemic Bias

Paola Di Maio

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Center for Systems, Knowledge Representation and Neuroscience

paola.dimaio@gmail.com

Abstract: Understanding and disentangling bias has become a priority for FAT (Fair Accountable and Transparent) AI. This research note introduces the notion of Systemic Bias, it is part of a larger body of work being produced in academic, industry and collaborative context with inputs from a diversity of stakeholders.

Keywords: AI, Systemic Bias

1. Accountability And Algorithmic Bias

Intelligent systems powered by algorithms have become pervasive and embedded, and algorithmic accountability is an imperative quality criterion for AI, whereby plausible justifications is necessary for reliable automated system's outputs. Many types of bias are identified and discussed in a growing body of Machine Learning literature [see references] and are being addressed in academic research as well in the praxis with initiatives that aim

to disseminate principles and good practices summarised as FAT (Fair Accountable and Transparent)¹. These include:

- **Responsibility:** Externally visible avenues of redress for adverse individual or societal effects, and designate an internal role for the person who is responsible for the timely remedy of such issues.
- **Explainability:** Ensure that algorithmic decisions as well as any data driving those decisions can be explained to end-users and other stakeholders in non-technical terms.
- **Accuracy:** Identify, log, and articulate sources of error and uncertainty so that expected and worst case implications can be understood and inform mitigation procedures.
- **Auditability:** Enable interested third parties to probe, understand, and review the behavior of the algorithm through disclosure of information that enables monitoring, checking, or criticism, including through provision of detailed documentation, technically suitable APIs, and permissive terms of use.
- **Fairness:** Ensure that algorithmic decisions do not create discriminatory or unjust impacts when comparing across different demographics (e.g. race, sex, etc).

Attempts are underway to devise a hierarchical conceptual structure such as a taxonomy for Bias, however this is proving challenging. The list of

¹

<https://www.fatml.org/resources/principles-for-accountable-algorithms>

biases is long, innumerable distortions and flaws characterize human thinking and consequently machines designed by humans. Biases can be grouped according to different needs and views and the choice of taxonomic arrangement is determined by the worldview, the task, the norms in the field of practice or discipline in which it is applied. When taking a systemic, high level view however, most types of biases can be arranged in a handful of clusters which are entangled and co-dependent, generating a type of bias which is defined here as 'systemic'. Systemic bias therefore can be defined as any bias that impacts the fairness and the accuracy of a system's outcome and that cannot be ascribed to a single factor, because its underlying causes are co-dependent.

2. Disentangling Systemic Bias

There exist different ways to categorize bias, depending on epistemological perspectives, constraints and other factors. Some types of bias are well understood and exist aside from AI implementation such as cognitive bias, research bias, etc. A single taxonomy of biases can be problematic and resource intensive to formulate, at the time of writing there have been no definitive results in this direction. However some broad categories can be generalized from literature and organised from the most basic level (perceptual) to the most generalized level (systemic) as follows:

Perceptual Perceptual biases are errors that disrupt and distort the perceptual process, thus leading to faulty judgements. These can occur because we, as humans, attempt to create shortcuts of understanding

Cognitive Tversky and Kahneman introduced the term 'cognitive bias' to describe people's systematic but purportedly flawed patterns of responses to judgment and decision problems. There are many kinds of cognitive biases [5]

Representational A representational bias defines the states in a search space. Typically, this search space is the space of hypotheses, a strong representational bias for the hypothesis space implies a small hypothesis space; a weak representational bias implies a large hypothesis space.[6] In addition, Representation Bias can be characterised further as a type of knowledge misrepresentation. Ie, if some fact is false, partially true, incomplete or placed out of context, this can give rise to misrepresentation, ie, the representation does not correspond to truth, it is also called a representation bias.

Epistemological Relating to demarcation, confirmation, and scientific method and experiment.

Ontological Philosophical bias relating to *basic implicit assumptions* what exist (ontology)

Procedural Procedural bias is where an unfair amount of pressure is applied to the subjects, forcing them to complete their responses quickly. For example, employees asked to fill out a questionnaire during

their break period are likely to rush, rather than reading the questions properly.

Systemic: Any bias that cannot be ascribed to a single cause and is generated by a combination of the other types of bias. Real world problem spaces such as systemic deviation are complex and the product of emergence and of the entanglement of different factors. Solutions cannot be found following a single path, biased outcomes cannot be attributed to a single variable in an algorithm. Similarly, when designing, implementing and deploying AI systems, due to the complexity of the interactions between controlled computational environments and real life deployments, it can be difficult to pinpoint system malfunction to a single factor resulting in systemic functional risks and functionally or ethically ‘wrong’ outcomes. Systemic bias is therefore defined as emergent from the combination of one or more or all of these types of high level bias groupings

Image: Systemic Bias

[...]

A functional level emerges from practice to evaluate adequacy according to a Level of KR reality task-domain-system model, the functional system level (Image 2)

Image 2

3. Algorithmic Auditability Checklist

It is unlikely that bias can be completely avoided, however, steps can be taken to reduce it and mitigate the adverse impact of bias in automated systems. Algorithmic auditing methods are being devised with such purpose. It is often argued that algorithmic auditing may not be entirely

automated due to the inherent lack of replicability of probabilistic causal computation, using a combination of different KR techniques in triangulation facilitates the explicit representation and replication, even partial, of artificial neural network computation. A sample checklist is synthesized from good practices in KR and offered here as a set of heuristic criteria to guide developers who may want to attempt creating an algorithm for algorithmic auditability, as well for auditors and developers of auditing methodologies:

Algorithmic Audit should identify and makes explicit:

Individuals/Components/Entities of the Algorithm

Axioms/Laws/Constraints/Limitations

Truth Values (consistency, persistence, conflicts)

Processes/Functions

Inputs/Outputs/Outcomes

Risks and Mitigation

Bias/De biasing options

Type Of Reasoning/Inference

Relevant Variables

Behaviours

8

Structure/Patterns

Levels Of Predictability Of The Behaviours (Probability, Randomness)

Influence Factors

Variables That May Influence Factors

Interactions

Type Of Notation/Encoding

Knowledge Level (Logical, Implementational, Epistemological, Conceptual, Linguistic, Task, Domain, System)

Overall Scientific/Computational Paradigm

Complete/Sufficiently Describing what it represents

Should Allow Manipulation Of The Representation For Testing/Evaluation Purposes

Human And Machine Readable

General FAT areas of concerns (Fairness Accountability Transparency)

4. Conclusion

This research note summarises a broad set of categories that can be referenced in knowledge organisation efforts in relation to bias, in

particular algorithmic bias. It defines and explain the notion of Systemic Bias, and includes a set of guiding criteria for algorithmic auditing, It is shared for reference and for discussion.

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